

THOUGHTS ON EAWAG

Janet G. Hering, Ph.D.
*Environmental Science & Engineering
California Institute of Technology*

*Zürich, Switzerland
5 November 2005*

EAWAG is a unique resource not only for Switzerland but also for the world.

Under Stumm, EAWAG established its reputation for outstanding fundamental studies of environmental systems.

Under Zehnder, EAWAG continued this tradition and also expanded its cutting-edge analytical and field capabilities. The focus of research was sharpened to emphasize AQUATIC systems but also broadened to include SOCIO-ECONOMIC aspects and to address issues in DEVELOPING COUNTRIES.

EAWAG's capabilities = people + facilities

→ (unique) opportunities

Goals

- Attract outstanding people.
- Provide environment that encourages excellence and builds synergies.
- Exploit EAWAG's unique capabilities (e.g., rapid response).
- Collaborate with ETHZ and EPFL to train next generation of environmental scientists and engineers.
- Identify and address problems of national and international importance.

Three approaches to identifying future avenues for advances in water research

Issue in current water research: sparseness of data

GEOSECS SAMPLING

- 66W-01W: 61 stations
- 44N-74N: 10 stations
- 61W-19E: 28 stations
- 58S: 11 stations
- measured parameters:
temperature, salinity, oxygen,
phosphate, silicate

Heroic efforts yet so incomplete

Java OceanAtlas
http://odf.ucsd.edu/joa/reid_data/nodcsd2/ATL/EDU__SET.ATL/map_geosecs_atl.html

Research needs: sensor technology

Desired characteristics

- multiple parameter sensitivity
- robust
- self-calibrating
- data-logging or linking
- inexpensive

<http://sfbay.wr.usgs.gov/access/wqdata/overview/measure/ctd/>

Implantable Blood Pressure and Flow Sensor
www.atdco.org/news/january282002.html

Issue in current water research: need for integration across scales

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As(III) surface complexes on (110) plane of goethite

Chesapeake Bay

Manning et al. (1998) *ES&T*, 32: 2383.

<http://www.cirla.org>

Societal needs: water conservation and re-use

Reduction in snowpack 1950-2000

Service (2004) *Science*, 303: 1124.

2000-2001 acre-ft spread in LA county	
storm runoff	144,599
imported water	58,448
recycled water	46,343

<http://ladpw.org/wrd/publication/system/index.cfm>

Natural vs. engineered systems: a false dichotomy

- Impact of human activities is global and not limited to (deliberately) engineered systems.
- Human beings are part of the biosphere, not separate from it.
 - ⇒ other species also cause global-scale effects
 - ⇒ other species also produce engineered artifacts
 - ⇒ human species has agency, consciousness of our actions and their effects
- Alternative view: continuum

First steps.....

Learn

- (more) about EAWAG
- about ETHZ and EPFL
- about Swiss environmental issues

Identify

- needs and opportunities
- future directions

Build

- new capabilities (people & facilities)

